

CITY-MOVE

City based interventions to stimulate active movement for health

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List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Meaning
EU	European Union
GAPPA	Global Action Plan on Physical Activity 2018-2030
GHG	GreenHouse Gas
NCD	Non-communicable diseases
PA	Physical Activity
ToC	Theory of Change
ULL	Urban Living Lab
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Projections indicate that by 2050 almost 70% of people will be living in cities. Creating healthy environments in complex urban environments challenges several sectors in different levels of government. The lack of physical activity in urban contexts is a significant global health issue that represents higher rates of non-communicable diseases which are leading causes of premature death. As a response to this challenge, the WHO has developed the Global Action Plan on Physical Activity 2018–2030 (GAPPA; WHO, 2019) to focus national efforts on promoting physical activity. GAPPA proposes four objectives and a set of 20 policy actions to help governments design, fund and monitor interventions that encourage citizens to be more active. Nevertheless, there is a lack of evidence on successful implementation and the enabling factors for PA interventions, and on how to enhance uptake and effects in low-income neighbourhoods and underserved and least active populations. Also, there is too little knowledge on how city's best structure can the governance for decision-making and implementation of GAPPA and which data can guide decision-making.

CITY-MOVE will address these gaps through the adaptation and implementation of the GAPPA actions to a city context (city-GAPPA) in six cities from three different continents (Africa, Europe and Latin America). It will develop a cross-contextual evaluation framework based upon a Theory of Change with the objective to enable researchers and implementers to take a system's perspective to the evaluation of the city-GAPPA interventions. This report presents the first version of CITY-MOVE ToC, developed collaboratively.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN CITIES

With 55% of the global population living in cities (United Nations), projected to reach 68% by 2050, urban areas face significant sustainability challenges. Cities are increasingly central to planning sustainable strategies and site-specific solutions for issues like climate change resilience, health, and biodiversity loss. Viewing **health as a central issue of urban configuration**, land use change (and competition), lack of basic infrastructure, facilities or housing all become part of the complexity that should be addressed by more comprehensive planning and multifunctional actions to create healthy urban environments. A central component in this policy field of sustainability and health is the (lack of) physical activity of people in urban environments.

The **lack of physical activity** in urban contexts is a significant global health issue. According to the World Health Organization, more than 80% of adolescents and 27% of adults worldwide do not meet the recommended levels of physical activity (Global status report on physical activity, 2022). Widespread inactivity is particularly pronounced in urban areas, where sedentary lifestyles are more common due to factors such as increased use of motorized transportation, limited access to recreational spaces, and high levels of occupational sitting. Urban environments, especially in resource limited settings, often lack (access to) the infrastructure necessary to promote physical activity, such as safe walking and cycling paths, parks, and recreational facilities. This deficiency contributes to higher rates of non-communicable diseases (NCDs) such as heart disease, stroke, cancer, and diabetes, which are leading causes of premature death (Fazeli et al., 2022).

It must be noted that many urban interventions that focus on physical activity are multifaceted and might **not have been primarily designed to address health**. For instance, improvement of the urban mobility network (including intermodal strategies to move better, faster and comfortably together) with the reduction of GreenHouse Gas (GHG) emissions due to use of active modes of transport, are strategies that primarily relate to climate change mitigation goals at urban scale (Glazener & Khreis, 2019). Improving urban mobility and reducing GHG are two of the commonly used drivers for modifying the way people move in cities and could lead to planning concepts such as the 10, 15 or 20min city, which promotes walking and bicycling to cut emissions and create a sustainable and healthy urban design (Logan et al., 2022).

Resident's wellbeing and health were once measured and reported as side effects or co-benefits of active transportation in cities, however they have gained importance more recently. For instance, there is compelling evidence of how the intensive use of carbon-based mobility

in cities influences the health of residents (Nieuwenhuijsen, 2020). As a response, the WHO has developed the **Global Action Plan on Physical Activity 2018–2030** (GAPPA; WHO, 2019) to focus national efforts on promoting physical activity. GAPPA proposes four objectives and a set of 20 policy actions to help governments design, fund and monitor interventions that encourage citizens to be more active.

The level of devolved power and decision-making a city government has, will also vary between and within countries. Urban interventions can reflect “top-down” (Government) or “bottom-up” (Grassroots or community) led initiatives. When examining health interventions, the context cities and their governments are imbedded within will influence several parameters, namely, who provides, what to whom, when, where, with what effect and for how long. Moreover, integration across urban sectors and various levels of government is essential for addressing global challenges such as climate change by empowering communities to make physically active choices. However, currently, there is a lack of evaluation evidence and routine data demonstrating the efficacy of such interventions.

CITY-MOVE will frame urban interventions with a “Physical Activity for Health” lens to understand how six cities, from three different regions around the globe, are adapting for more active people, societies, environments and systems.

1.3. CITY-MOVE RATIONALE FOR A TOC

The World Health Organization (WHO), GAPPA (GAPPA; WHO, 2019), has been created to focus efforts, at a national scale, and proposes four objectives and a set of 20 policy actions that could help governments to propose and resource interventions that support their citizens to be more active. The systems-based approach to policy implementation outlines how sectors of the system (in this case, urban society) can provide integral solutions that tackle global challenges such as climate change by empowering communities to make physically active choices such as changes in transportation or recreation, have many benefits. **GAPPA**, however, **lacks evidence to boost implementation**. There is a lack of evidence on successful implementation and the enabling factors for the interventions, and on how to enhance uptake and effects in low-income neighbourhoods and underserved and least active populations. There is too little knowledge on how city’s best structure can the governance for decision-making and implementation of GAPPA and which data can guide decision-making.

1.4. PURPOSE OF THE CITY-MOVE-TOC

CITY-MOVE will address the above knowledge and practice gaps through the adaptation and implementation of the GAPPA actions to a city context (city-GAPPA) in six cities from three different continents. It will develop a cross-contextual evaluation framework based upon a Theory of Change (ToC) with the objective to enable researchers and implementers to take a system's perspective to the evaluation of the city-GAPPA interventions. The ToC should consider the combination and sequencing of interventions and their relationship with the city context core elements and key stakeholders.

The combinations of early and late interventions in each city comprise different GAPPA domains, and the learning across 6 city contexts in three continents greatly enhances the depth and scale of lessons generated by CITY-MOVE. Recognizing the complexity and diverse contexts of cities and regions, the CITY-MOVE's ambition is to provide a legacy ToC based on empirical evidence of **all 20 GAPPA actions** that offer a roadmap for local governments and stakeholders to design, resource, operate, and monitor health (or multipurpose) interventions, accommodating local needs and circumstances. Therefore, CITY-MOVE ToC should guide decisions on transferability and scalability of interventions.

2. METHOD

2.1. DEFINITION OF CITY

City can mean different things to different people and governments; the number of inhabitants, the size of the urbanized area, the density of inhabitants, or infrastructure installed in a given area (Dijkstra, et al., 2021). In the CITY-MOVE project, the concept of city is taken as “a contiguous territory inhabited at urban density levels without regard to administrative boundaries” and refers to urban agglomerations that encompass urban and peri-urban areas (ONUHABITAT, 2020). Six cities, in six different countries, are involved in CITY-MOVE, namely,

Antwerp, Belgium, Europe – The country's third largest city has a metropolitan population of 1,230,000 (565,039 municipality residents), across the metropolitan area of 1,449 km² (municipality city size is 208.22 km²) with an elevation of 8 m above sea level.

Bogotá, Columbia, Latin America – The country's capital city and one of the largest cities in the world has a metropolitan population of 11,658,211 (8,034,649 capital city residents) across an area of 5,934 km² (capital city size is 1,587 km²) with an elevation of 2,640 m above sea level.

Kampala, Uganda, Africa - The country's capital city has a metropolitan population of 6,709,900 (1,680,600 capital city residents) across an area of 8,451.9 km² (capital city size is 189 km²) with an elevation of 1,200 m above sea level.

Lima, Peru, Latin America - The country's capital city has a metropolitan population of 11,283,787 (10,092,000 capital city residents) across an area of 2,819.3 km² (capital city size is 2,672.3 km²) with an elevation of 0-100 m above sea level.

Ljubljana, Slovenia, Europe - The country's capital city has a metropolitan population of 537,893 (288,382 capital city residents) across an area of 2,334 km² (capital city size is 163.8 km²) with an elevation of 295 m above sea level.

Rotterdam, the Netherlands, Europe - The country's second largest city has a metropolitan population of 664,311, across an area of 324.14 km² with an elevation of -2 m below sea level.

The 6 countries involved in CITY-MOVE have varying degrees of urbanization. Belgium and the Netherlands already have more than 90% of their populations residing in urban areas, by contrast, Slovenia has approximately 55% of its population living in cities. These countries, guided by common EU or national targets, typically implement robust sustainability policies in urban planning. Rapid urbanization rates are also evident in Peru and Colombia, where over 80% of the population reside in cities, many of whom, live in vulnerable conditions due to the significant influx of people from rural areas with limited land use management capacity. In contrast, Southern African countries such as Uganda still have the majority of the population (around 74%) living in rural areas. Despite the differing degrees of urbanization, urban areas in these countries all face challenges in providing adequate infrastructure, facilities, and housing for all inhabitants, alongside the infrastructure needed to accommodate high levels of commuting via informal transportation (Behrens, McCormick & Mnanga, 2016).

2.2. BUILDING A TOC

Theories or models are used to assist in predicting how change will happen (process) and enable the identification of appropriate factors or indicators. The Theory of Change can be defined simply as a theory of how and why an initiative can work (Connell & Kubisch, 1998; Weiss, 1995). Applied during the design phase, and normally based on evidence, theories of change have been widely used since the 1980's in different fields of practice. They outline how the intervention is expected to result in desirable outcomes by mapping out key elements of change such as impacts, activities, outputs, contextual factors, assumptions or expectations of how the intervention works and the mechanisms of change which will lead to the desired outcomes.

The Aspen Institute developed the Theory of Change Approach as a method to help evaluate complex community initiatives. This approach acknowledges the complexity of working with multiple components and multiple levels. The process is one of co-construction drawing on

existing knowledge and insights from stakeholders. Connell and Kubisch (1998) argue that a good ToC should be plausible, doable and testable. A ToC has been developed for CITY-MOVE to capture the complexity of multiple interventions, in multiple cities that achieve the shared outcome of increases physical activity of city residents. A ToC is a specification of pathway(s) to change through interventions and it supports the active delivery (Ghate, 2018). According to Laing and Todd (2015), there are four types of ToC that can be used for development, research and evaluation. The first is a *Deductive Model* which is developed from existing literature, research and knowledge about how the world works. An *Inductive Model* is built from observing practice and assumptions about how things work. A *Mental Model* utilises the knowledge and experience of stakeholders. Finally, the *Collaborative Model* is co-created through collaboration between academic expertise (inputting evidence from existing research) and practice expertise (where stakeholders outline their view of how things work). Using the collaborative model, the researcher takes the position of a critical friend offering support and challenge to the views of stakeholders. As an example of collaborative ToC “The Little Book of Theory of Change for Infrastructure and Cities” (Rogers et al., 2022) was created with the purpose of transforming infrastructure and urban systems *to enable safe, resilient and sustainable living, and to generate wellbeing and prosperity for all*. Divided in 4 spheres named, control, direct influence, indirect influence and impact, The Little Book embedded stakeholders throughout the change process, leaving space for evaluation and decision-making during the ToC development.

In **CITY-MOVE**, a collaborative model will be constructed in partnership with stakeholders from a combination of existing and emerging interventions and using relevant literature, policy documents and empirical research. Whilst, ToC are ideally employed in the early development phase, there are examples of retrospective construction of ToC. Therefore, CITY-MOVE ToC has been developed to capture all the interventions involved in the project (named early and late interventions).

The interventions were firstly related to GAPPA dimensions and principles to understand the PA context and core elements in each city, together with the group of stakeholders responsible for developing and implementing the initiative (to be further presented as D.1.3). Therefore, the CITY-MOVE ToC will be embedded in, but also contribute to a city scale GAPPA.

A consultation process was designed for integrating different perspectives from CITY-MOVE participants on the ToC. It flows to and backwards a common CITY-MOVE ToC framework, where CITY-MOVE research team (01), external experts (02) and local stakeholders (03) may collaborate directly or indirectly. Local stakeholders will be accessed during the activities planned in the Urban Living Labs (ULL) in each city, developed by WP2, with the help of a “Tool Kit for urban interventions”. The tool kit has a logic model imbedded in its structure to help local teams in designing, implementing and monitoring PA interventions. Therefore, through the application of this tool CITY-MOVE will recollect information, evaluate whether common issues can be extract from each city and enrich the first version of CITY-MOVE legacy ToC (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: CITY-MOVE consultation process to a ToC common framework.

Figure 01: CITY-MOVE consultation process to a ToC common framework.

The set of 6 stages for developing a ToC, proposed by The Centre for Theory of Change, a not-for-profit organisation established by ActKnowledge in New York guided the definition of the visual graph used by CITY-MOVE ToC. The 6 stages are listed,

1. Identifying long-term goals
2. Backwards mapping and connecting the preconditions or requirements necessary to achieve that goal and explaining why these preconditions are necessary and sufficient.
3. Identifying your basic assumptions about the context.
4. Identifying the interventions that your initiative will perform to create your desired change.
5. Developing indicators to measure your outcomes to assess the performance of your initiative.
6. Writing a narrative to explain the logic of your initiative.

Therefore, **CITY-MOVE** proposes the first general structure for its ToC. Based on the description of the *Reality*, the definition of key *Activities and Resources* to achieve desirable *Outputs and Outcomes* the model should successfully guide a city to achieve long-term *Impact*. The model should be completed backwards (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: CITY-MOVE ToC model components.

3. A PRELIMINARY RESULT

3.1. DEVELOPMENT TIMELINE

The ToC started being developed during the first year of City Move with the aim to provide researchers with a framework to understand the relationships between the activities, outputs and outcomes, focus on long term impact of PA interventions.

The initial development of the ToC involved a workshop with CITY-MOVE researchers (TM, RL, JO, EW) in May 2024 during the Bogotá public launch of the project. This involved initial discussions of perceived key elements of the ToC and how these elements would be spatially represented (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: First CITY-MOVE ToC workshop during Bogotá's meeting.

Through a number of follow-up meetings with this group and additional input from work package leads (JE, LV) a series of iterations of the ToC emerged. Additionally, a decision regarding the most appropriate ToC representation was made by WP 1 leads. This framework and ToC draft was shared with the wider CITY-MOVE team and feedback invited (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Consultation version of ToC model shared with CITY-MOVE researchers.

3.1. FIRST VERSION OF CITY-MOVE ToC

To assist in building the first version of the ToC, those interventions named as “early”, assisted in sharing information on important stakeholders, collaboration and engagement methods. This information sharing took place as part of a Stakeholder mapping activity through workshops with intervention teams in 2024 (part of WP 1). The information gathered from the stakeholder mapping exercise was incorporated into the development of the ToC (see Figure 5).

Another key adaptation of the model was the inclusion of a reflective cycle between *Activities and Resources* and *Outputs*. The proposal was to provide a space for learn, adapt and (re) experiment during the development of the ToC. This step is also presented in the co-creation process conducted by Active Researchers in each ULL.

The information was filled backwards and have the following content:

Impact: “Cities develop a contextually relevant (political and policy) whole-of-system approach to reduce health inequalities”.

Outcome: a CITY-MOVE GAPPA Roadmap and toolkit that enables the transferability of lessons learned to other cities, target groups and contexts.

Output: an implementation strategy, together with a Decision - Making analysis framework are developed to bring the necessary information to establishing an evaluation strategy. A repository of outputs and tools will then be generated to make it possible to achieve the Outcomes.

Activities and Resources: are embedded in the understanding of how interventions relate to GAPPA dimensions and principles. Activities are divided into: Understand core context elements; stakeholders mapping; capacity building and co-creation process; and Multicriteria Decision Making Analysis. Activities are related between each other and together will result in the described outputs.

Reality: CITY-MOVE identified four main gaps cities face to implement interventions aimed to promote physical activities:

- a) under-implemented
- b) a whole-of-system approach particularly lacking
- c) often fail to target the least active or vulnerable groups
- d) too little attention to political and policy context

This reality will be considered when proposing activities to achieve the desired impact.

Figure 5: First version of CITY-MOVE ToC model.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. REFLECTION ON PROCESS

The CITY-MOVE GAPPA ToC is being built collaboratively. Actively listening to different voices incorporating the lived experience and expertise from multiple stakeholders enriches the process but demands time and a high capacity of synthesis. The aim of the ToC is to bring a common framework, translated as a roadmap for taking action.

4.2. RISKS AND LIMITATIONS

Despite the above-cited advantages, it is important to acknowledge and consider common risks or limitations when applying ToC. ToC might sound unrealistic as they often fail to consider political pressures (among other, social, economic and cultural issues), that can impact policy makers in their decision making and practice. The theoretical intention to build a collaborative environment where different stakeholders can have voice, but, in practice, not all voices are equal, usually the policy makers dominate the debate (Bolton, Martin, Grace & Harris, 2018). Also, It is quite common to find overly complicated models, including those that over claim, miss specify or are unclear in defining outcomes, or elements that do not follow a logical flow.

4.3. WAY FORWARD

During the next two and a half years of the CITY-MOVE project's lifespan, information will be gathered specifically through co-creation activities run as part of the ULLs in each city (WP2). As a capacity building strategy, the ULL aims to strengthen the cities to better plan PA interventions for health. The Multicriteria- Decision Analysis (WP5) will systematize the results and identify the expected impacts from each intervention. Activities from WP1, WP3 and WP4 will contribute to the enrichment information gathered and thereby, inform the legacy ToC. Therefore, the expectation is to adapt the first version of CITY-MOVE ToC, presented in this document (D.1.1), into a useful resource for different groups of stakeholders to boost PA in cities across the globe.

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